

INFLUENCE OF DOSES OF NITROGEN FERTILIZERS ON THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF AMARANTH PLANTS

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Annotation. The article presents data on the effect of nitrogen fertilizer norms on the chemical composition of amaranth plants, that is, the content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in various plant organs. The application of nitrogen fertilizers at a rate of 150 to 300 kg/ha against the background of phosphorus-potassium fertilizers contributed to an increase in the content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in grain, above-ground biomass, crop residues and roots of amaranth plants. At the same time, nitrogen fertilizers had a different effect on increasing the content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in different plant organs.

Keywords: amaranth, plants, nitrogen fertilizers, norm, chemical composition, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium

Determining the chemical composition of the amaranth plant is of great importance for determining the nutrient needs of plants and assessing product quality[1;2;3;4;5]. Determining the amount of elements nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium is important in assessing plant nutrition. The content of total nitrogen in amaranth grain in the control without fertilization was 2.54%, and in the background variant P150K200, where only phosphate and potash fertilizers were applied, it was 2.55%. As a result of the use of nitrogen fertilizers, the amount of nitrogen in amaranth grain increased to 2.56-2.58%. The content of nitrogen in the grain increased with the increase in the rate of nitrogen fertilizers. Only against the background of the introduction of P150K200 with an increase in the rate of nitrogen fertilizers from 250 kg/ha to 300 kg/ha, the amount of nitrogen in the grain did not change.

The content of phosphorus in grain increased both under the influence of phosphate fertilizers and under the influence of nitrogen fertilizers. For example, in the control variant without fertilization, the phosphorus content in the grain was 0.44% relative to the absolute dry matter, in the background variant P150K200, where only phosphorus and potash fertilizers were used, this figure was 0.49%, against this background, when nitrogen fertilizers were applied at the rate of 150-300 kg/ha, it was 0.49-0.50%.

The content of potassium in amaranth grain was 1.12% in the control without fertilization. In the case of the background variant P150K200, the potassium content in the grain was 1.13%, while when nitrogen fertilizers were applied at different rates, this figure was 1.14-1.15%. The content of potassium in amaranth grain increased at a nitrogen fertilizer rate of 150 kg/ha and when this rate was increased to 200 kg/ha. An increase in the rate of nitrogen fertilizers from 200 kg/ha to 250 and 300 kg/ha did not affect the potassium content in the grain.

Consequently, nitrogen fertilizers increase the amount of nitrogen in the grain with an increase in their dose to 250 kg/ha. The maximum amount of phosphorus and potassium in the grain was reached when nitrogen fertilizers were applied at the rate of 200 kg/ha. An increase in the rate of nitrogen fertilizers from 200 kg/ha to 250 and 300 kg/ha did not lead to an increase in the content of phosphorus and potassium in the grain.

The content of total nitrogen in the aboveground biomass of the amaranth plant ranged from 1.70-1.72%. At the same time, the amount of nitrogen in the above-ground biomass of amaranth on the unfertilized control variant was 1.70%, while on the background variant P150K200 this figure was 1.71%, and on the background+N150, background+N200 variants - 1.71% and 1.72% respectively. Against this background, an increase in the rate of nitrogen fertilizers from 200 kg/ha to 250 kg/ha and up to 300 kg/ha did not affect the nitrogen content in the aboveground amaranth biomass.

The content of phosphorus in the aboveground biomass of amaranth plants with different fertilizer systems is about 0.50-0.52%, with the application of only phosphorus and potash fertilizers - 0.51%, with the application of nitrogen fertilizers at a rate of 150 kg / ha - 0.51% , and on the options Background + N200 and Background + N250 it was 0.52%, in the option Background + N300 - 0.51%. An increase in the rate of nitrogen fertilizers from 250 kg/ha to 300 kg/ha led to a slight decrease in the amount of phosphorus in the aboveground biomass. The content of potassium in the above-ground biomass of amaranth increased both under the influence of phosphorus-potassium and nitrogen fertilizers. An increase in the content of potassium in the aboveground biomass was noted when nitrogen fertilizers were applied at a high dose - 250-300 kg/ha. For example, if in the control variant without fertilization the potassium content in the above-ground biomass was 2.35%, then in the background variant P150K200 this indicator was 2.36%, in the

variants background+N150, background+N200, background-N250, background+N300 2.36, 2.36, 2.37, 2.37% respectively.

The nitrogen content in amaranth crop residues ranged from 1.54-1.59%. In the background variant R150K200, where only phosphorus and potash fertilizers were used, it was 1.56%, and in the variants where nitrogen fertilizers were used at a rate of 150,200,250,300 kg/ha, this figure was 1.57; 1.58; 1.59; 1.59% respectively. With an increase in the rate of nitrogen fertilizers from 250 kg/ha to 300 kg/ha, the nitrogen content in the crop residues of amaranth plants did not change. The content of phosphorus in the crop residues of the amaranth culture varied within 0.53-0.56%. With the combined use of phosphorus and potash fertilizers in the background variant, the amount of phosphorus in crop residues was 0.55%, in the background + N150, background + N200, background + N250, background + N300 options, this figure was 0.55; 0.56; 0.56; 0.56% respectively.

The content of potassium in crop residues increased under the influence of fertilizers. For example, if in the control variant without fertilization the amount of potassium in crop residues was 2.33%, then in the background variant it was 2.34%, in the variants with nitrogen fertilizer application at the rate of 150, 200, 250, 300 c/ha - 2.34%; 2.35; 2.35; 2.36% respectively. Therefore, when nitrogen fertilizers are applied in high doses, the potassium content in amaranth plants is increased.

The nitrogen content in amaranth roots was about 1.17-1.21%. The use of phosphorus and potash fertilizers increased the nitrogen content in the amaranth root. The nitrogen content in amaranth roots increased when nitrogen fertilizers were applied in high doses (150-300 kg/ha). For example, the nitrogen content in the amaranth root in the control variant without fertilization was 1.17%, in the background variant P150K200 - 1.18%, in the variants background + N150, background + N200, background + N250, background + N300 - 1.19 ; 1.20; 1.21; 1.21% respectively. Fertilizers also affected the phosphorus content of the roots. At the same time, the content of phosphorus in the roots on the control variant without fertilizer was 0.60%, on the background variant P150K200 it was 0.61%, background + N150, Background + N200, Background + N250 and background + N300 - 0.61; 0.61; 0.62; 0.61% respectively. Consequently, nitrogen fertilizers at an application rate of 250 kg/ha increase the amount of phosphorus in the root.

The amount of potassium in the roots ranged from 1.85-1.87% according to the variants of the experiment. Nitrogen fertilizers affected the amount of

potassium in the roots, the largest amount of potassium in the roots was observed when nitrogen fertilizers were applied at the rate of 200-300 kg/ha. Thus, nitrogen fertilizers affect the content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in all parts of the amaranth plant (grain, aboveground biomass, crop residues, root), while the concentration of these elements increases.

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